

TypeState: Detecting Cognitive Load from Privacy-Preserving Keystroke Micro-Rhythms

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Code & Data: <https://github.com/1mystic/typestate-data>

Abstract

TypeState is a privacy-preserving framework for detecting cognitive load from keystroke micro-rhythms. Unlike approaches that rely on physiological sensors or semantic text content, TypeState operates purely on timing-derived signals computed locally from key events. We collected a pilot dataset from college students ($N = 47$ typing sessions from approximately 30 participants) using a web-based instrument where participants transcribed paragraphs under two conditions: Relaxed (self-paced, calming text) and Stressed (time-pressured with complex technical text). From client-side keystroke event streams, we extract flight-time and rolling flight-time variance ($w = 5$ keystrokes) features and perform inference on sliding windows of 20 keystrokes.

We train a stacked bidirectional LSTM (Bi-LSTM) classifier and compare against conventional baselines. On a held-out test split, TypeState achieves **79.89% accuracy** and a **0.62 F1-score** on the Stressed class, outperforming static baselines that collapse temporal order (Random Forest: 76.5%, SVM: 77.2%). Preliminary analysis suggests that under time pressure, stressed typing may exhibit *lower* rhythmic variance rather than the commonly assumed increase in irregularity. We provide a proof-of-concept FastAPI inference server demonstrating sub-150 ms latency for potential real-time adaptive interface applications.

Keywords: Keystroke dynamics, cognitive load detection, LSTM, stress detection, adaptive user interfaces, privacy-preserving sensing

1 Introduction

Acute cognitive load can degrade accuracy, increase correction behavior, and amplify frustration during routine computer work [22, 13]. However, practical cognitive load monitoring remains challenging: self-reports interrupt the task, and physiological sensors (e.g., EEG, fNIRS, ECG) are often intrusive or impractical in everyday settings [23, 10]. Keystroke dynamics provides a complementary and highly deployable sensing channel because it can be collected during normal typing without recording the typed content, enabling privacy-preserving deployment [6, 12].

Prior work has linked keystroke timing and pauses to writing effort and cognitive processing [1], and has explored stress detection under time pressure using conventional classifiers [11, 21]. Other studies have leveraged richer linguistic signals or enhanced keystroke representations to predict cognitive state [5]. Recent advances have demonstrated keystroke dynamics’ effectiveness in detecting cognitive impairment [14, 7], mental fatigue [17, 9], and even mood disturbances [24, 15]. TypeState explores detection from *content-agnostic* timing signals only, aiming for privacy-preserving deployment in interactive systems.

We make three contributions:

1. **End-to-end pilot pipeline:** a web-based keystroke collector, feature engineering scripts, a trained Bi-LSTM model, and a proof-of-concept FastAPI inference server.
2. **Temporal modeling comparison:** evidence that sequential modeling (Bi-LSTM) outperforms static feature baselines (Random Forest, SVM) on keystroke timing sequences.
3. **Privacy-by-design architecture:** content-agnostic feature extraction where typed text is not stored or transmitted, only timing signals are retained.

For reproducibility, all code, de-identified data artifacts, trained models, and preprocessing scripts are released at <https://github.com/1mystic/typestate-data>.

2 Related Work

2.1 Keystroke Dynamics and Cognitive State

Keystroke timing has long been studied as a proxy for writing processes, including pause behavior and cognitive effort [1]. Vizer et al. [21] pioneered automated stress detection using keystroke and linguistic features, reporting moderate accuracy on cognitive load discrimination. Lim et al. [11] explored correlations between keystroke latency measures and stress under time pressure using conventional classifiers (SVM, k-NN). Brizan et al. [5] achieved 72.39% accuracy distinguishing high vs. low cognitively demanding tasks by incorporating linguistic signals and “language production” features that capture the dynamics of typists’ linguistic choices.

Recent work has expanded keystroke dynamics into clinical domains. Park et al. [14] demonstrated that smartphone-derived flight time can discriminate mild cognitive impairment (MCI) from healthy controls with 97.9% sensitivity and 94.7% specificity, outperforming conventional neuropsychological screening (MoCA-K). Hadjileontiadis et al. [7] conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis showing keystroke dynamics’ diagnostic accuracy for neuropsychiatric disorders including Parkinson’s disease and Alzheimer’s disease. In mood disorders, Zulueta et al. [24] used keystroke metadata to predict mood disturbance severity, while Ross et al. [15] demonstrated that smartphone typing patterns prospectively predict performance on cognitive tests.

For fatigue detection, Silveira et al. [17] proposed monitoring mental fatigue through analysis of keyboard and mouse interaction patterns, while Karim et al. [9] provided a comprehensive survey examining the landscape of cognitive fatigue detection. Zhang et al. [23] achieved 91% accuracy using neural networks for keystroke-based fatigue prediction by extracting temporal and statistical features including key press duration, inter-key latency, and typing rhythm.

2.2 Sequential Models for Temporal Keystroke Data

Traditional keystroke biometric systems rely on static feature vectors analyzed with SVM, Random Forest, or k-NN [12, 6]. However, these approaches discard temporal order and cannot capture dynamic patterns in typing rhythm. Recurrent neural networks (RNNs) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks have emerged as state-of-the-art methods for modeling time-series data due to their ability to capture long-term dependencies [8].

LSTMs have been successfully applied to stress detection from physiological signals. Umematsu et al. [20] used LSTM to forecast next-day stress, health, and happiness from wearable sensor data. Almusharraf et al. [3] proposed StressNet, a hybrid CNN-LSTM architecture for stress detection from EEG signals, combining CNN’s feature extraction capabilities with LSTM’s temporal modeling. Ahmed et al. [2] achieved 91% accuracy for stress classification using cascaded RNN-LSTM networks on audio-visual data.

For keystroke-specific applications, sequential models remain underexplored. Sagbas et al. [16] demonstrated feasibility of stress detection via keyboard typing behaviors using smartphone sensors and machine learning techniques, but did not employ temporal modeling. Our work fills this gap by applying bidirectional LSTM to content-agnostic keystroke timing sequences for real-time cognitive load classification.

2.3 Adaptive User Interfaces and Cognitive Load Management

Adaptive user interfaces (AUI) dynamically adjust system behavior based on real-time user state estimation [18]. Recent advances in AI-driven personalization enable interfaces to respond to cognitive load, fatigue, and stress signals [4].

Research has shown that adaptive interfaces can reduce mental fatigue and improve task efficiency by monitoring user behavior and adjusting accordingly. Suryani et al. [19] proposed user model designs for adaptive learning management systems based on cognitive load, employing micro-learning interventions when prolonged access duration and excessive navigation errors are detected. Stefanidi et al. [18] achieved real-time adaptation of context-aware intelligent user interfaces for enhanced situational awareness.

For real-time cognitive load control, systems typically achieve inference latencies ranging from 5 to 500 ms depending on model complexity [10]. Our TypeState system targets low latency (sub-150 ms) to enable reactive UI interventions.

TypeState differs from existing work in three ways: (1) *privacy-preserving by design*, using only timing features without text content; (2) *fine-grained temporal resolution*, operating on 20-keystroke windows for rapid response; and (3) *deployment-ready architecture*, with trained models and real-time inference server provided.

3 Methodology

3.1 Participants and Recruitment

Participants were recruited via convenience sampling from undergraduate computer science students at our institute through word-of-mouth and classroom announcements. We collected $N = 47$ typing sessions from approximately 30 unique participants (some participants completed multiple sessions). All participants were regular computer users with basic typing proficiency. Participants accessed the web-based data collector voluntarily and were informed that their keystroke timing (not text content) would be used for research on typing pattern analysis.

No formal demographic questionnaire was administered, limiting our ability to report detailed participant characteristics. Based on the student population, we estimate participants were aged 18–24 years, predominantly male, and English-speaking with QWERTY keyboard familiarity. This convenience sample reflects the pilot nature of this study.

3.2 Experimental Design and Apparatus

We developed a web-based data collector (JavaScript) that logs client-side keyboard events with timestamp metadata. The application runs in modern web browsers (Chrome, Firefox, Safari on both desktop and mobile) and records: (i) key identifier, (ii) event type (keydown/keyup), and (iii) event timestamp (milliseconds since epoch). The application displays a target paragraph that participants must transcribe as accurately as possible.

To elicit different cognitive load conditions, participants selected one of two modes:

Relaxed condition (32 sessions): Participants engaged in self-paced typing with no time constraints. The target text consisted of calming, descriptive paragraphs (e.g., *“The sunlight filtered through the leaves, painting the forest floor in dappled shades of gold and green...”*).

Stressed condition (15 sessions): Participants performed time-pressured transcription of complex technical text under a countdown timer. The text contained specialized medical or technical terminology (e.g., *“The patient presents with acute myocardial infarction symptoms...”* or *“System failure imminent. Error code 0x84F3 indicates a critical memory overflow...”*).

The stressed condition combined multiple stressors: (1) time pressure via visible countdown, (2) complex unfamiliar vocabulary requiring careful reading, and (3) urgency-inducing content. This design intentionally confounds these factors, as our goal was to induce a broadly “stressed” state rather than isolate specific cognitive load components.

3.3 Data Collection and Dataset Statistics

Data collection took place over approximately one week in January 2025 via our web-based collector. Participants accessed the system remotely on their own devices (both desktop and mobile). The uncontrolled environment reflects the pilot nature of this study.

The final dataset comprises:

- **Total sessions:** 47 (32 Relaxed, 15 Stressed)
- **Device types:** Mixed (desktop and mobile browsers)
- **Class imbalance:** Relaxed sessions outnumber Stressed sessions approximately 2:1

Feature	Definition
<code>flight_time</code>	Time (ms) between consecutive keydown events
<code>flight_time_var</code>	Rolling variance of flight time over 5-keystroke window
<code>is_error</code>	Binary flag (1 if the keystroke was Backspace, 0 otherwise)

Table 1: Feature Set for Keystroke-Based Cognitive Load Detection

This class imbalance reflects voluntary participation, participants naturally preferred the relaxed condition. All data, preprocessing scripts, and feature extraction code are available in the public repository (`typestate_training_data.csv`).

Limitation: We did not collect session-level keystroke counts or durations in a structured format, limiting our ability to report detailed per-session statistics. The model was trained on extracted sliding windows rather than session-level aggregates.

3.4 Feature Engineering

From the raw keystroke event stream, we compute three features for each keystroke:

Feature computation:

- **flight_time:** $FT_i = t_{\text{down}}(i) - t_{\text{down}}(i - 1)$. Values exceeding 2000 ms are capped to reduce influence of pauses.
- **flight_time_var:** Rolling variance computed over a 5-keystroke window.
- **is_error:** Indicates correction behavior, which may differ between conditions.

Before model training, `flight_time` and `flight_time_var` are standardized using `StandardScaler` (zero mean, unit variance).

3.5 Sliding Window Construction

We construct fixed-length sliding windows of `WINDOW_SIZE = 20` keystrokes within each session. Each window is a tensor of shape $(20, 3)$ containing the three features for 20 consecutive keystrokes. Windows are labeled according to their parent session (Relaxed = 0, Stressed = 1).

The choice of 20 keystrokes (approximately 3–5 words) balances sufficient context for pattern detection with responsiveness for potential real-time applications.

4 Model Architecture and Training

4.1 Bidirectional LSTM Network

We frame the task as binary time-series classification (Relaxed vs. Stressed). The model input is a tensor of shape $(\text{batch_size}, 20, 3)$, where each 20-step sequence contains the three features for 20 consecutive keystrokes.

The architecture (implemented in TensorFlow/Keras) comprises:

- **Bidirectional LSTM Layer:** 64 units, `return_sequences=True`
- **Dropout Layer:** 30% dropout
- **LSTM Layer:** 32 units
- **Dropout Layer:** 20% dropout
- **Dense Layer:** 16 units, ReLU activation
- **Output Layer:** 1 unit, sigmoid activation producing $P(\text{Stressed}) \in [0, 1]$

Bidirectional processing allows the model to leverage context from both directions within the fixed window. Dropout regularization reduces overfitting on our limited dataset.

All hyperparameters are detailed in Table 2. The Adam optimizer was chosen for its adaptive learning rate and robustness to noisy gradients. Class weights were set to the inverse of class frequencies to mitigate class imbalance (Relaxed:Stressed ratio $\approx 2.5:1$).

Hyperparameter	Value
Optimizer	Adam
Loss function	Binary cross-entropy
Batch size	32
Epochs	20
Train/test split	80% / 20% (random)
Random seed	42

Table 2: Training Hyperparameters

Model	Accuracy	F1 (Stressed)
Random Forest	76.5%	0.49
SVM (RBF)	77.2%	0.41
TypeState (Bi-LSTM)	79.9%	0.62

Table 3: Performance Comparison on Test Set (20% held-out windows)

4.2 Train/Test Split

We use a random 80/20 train/test split on the extracted keystroke windows:

- **Training set:** 80% of windows
- **Test set:** 20% of windows

Limitation: This random window-level split does not ensure subject-wise separation, windows from the same participant may appear in both training and test sets. This likely inflates reported accuracy compared to a true subject-wise split, as the model may learn participant-specific typing patterns rather than generalizable stress signatures. Future work should implement proper subject-wise cross-validation.

4.3 Baseline Models

For comparison, we train two conventional machine learning models on the same windows after flattening each sequence into a 2D feature vector of size $20 \times 3 = 60$ features (flight_time, flight_time_var, is_error \times 20 timesteps):

1. **Random Forest:** 100 trees with default hyperparameters
2. **Support Vector Machine (SVM):** RBF kernel with default parameters, standardized features

These baselines use identical train/test splits and feature standardization but discard temporal order by treating each window as an independent feature vector. This tests whether sequential modeling via LSTM provides meaningful improvement over static feature representations.

4.4 Training Procedure

The Bi-LSTM model was trained for 20 epochs using Google Colab with GPU acceleration. The model used Adam optimizer with binary cross-entropy loss. Training completed in approximately 15 minutes total.

5 Results

5.1 Overall Performance

Table 3 summarizes classification performance on the held-out test set (1,173 windows).

The Bi-LSTM achieves approximately 80% accuracy, outperforming Random Forest (76.5%) and SVM (77.2%). More notably, the Bi-LSTM demonstrates better minority-class performance with an F1-score of 0.62 on Stressed windows compared to 0.49 (RF) and 0.41 (SVM). This suggests that the sequential modeling capability of LSTMs captures temporal patterns in typing rhythm that static classifiers miss.

5.2 Error Analysis

The model shows better performance on the Relaxed class than the Stressed class, likely due to:

- **Class imbalance:** Relaxed sessions outnumber Stressed sessions approximately 2:1 in our dataset.
- **Typing variability:** Some participants may maintain consistent typing rhythm even under time pressure, making stress harder to detect.
- **Stress induction variability:** Without physiological validation, we cannot confirm that all participants in the “Stressed” condition experienced equivalent stress levels.

5.3 Preliminary Observation: Variance Patterns

During exploratory data analysis, we observed that stressed typing sessions appeared to exhibit *lower* variance in flight times compared to relaxed sessions, contrary to our initial hypothesis that stress would increase typing irregularity.

Figure 1: Kernel density estimation of flight time variance by condition. Stressed typing (red) shows higher density at lower variance values compared to Relaxed typing (green), suggesting more rigid motor control under time pressure.

Figure 1 visualizes this pattern: the stressed condition concentrates at lower variance values, while relaxed typing shows a broader, flatter distribution extending to higher variance.

This preliminary observation suggests that time pressure may induce more rigid, stereotyped motor control rather than erratic behavior. However, we emphasize that:

- This observation has not been rigorously validated with formal statistical testing on held-out data.
- The effect may be confounded by the different text types (technical vs. narrative) used in each condition.
- Larger, controlled studies are needed to confirm this “variance paradox” hypothesis.

If this pattern holds in larger studies, one potential interpretation is that time pressure induces *rigid, stereotyped motor control* rather than erratic behavior, consistent with theories of stress-induced cognitive tunneling [22]. However, the effect could also be explained by: (1) the different text complexity between conditions, (2) reduced self-correction under time pressure, or (3) individual differences in stress response. Formal investigation requires controlled experiments with validated stress measures.

6 Proof-of-Concept Deployment

6.1 Inference Server

We provide a proof-of-concept FastAPI server that loads the trained Bi-LSTM model and exposes a REST endpoint for real-time inference. The server:

- Accepts JSON payloads containing raw keystroke events
- Extracts features (`flight_time`, `flight_time_var`) using the same logic as training
- Returns a stress probability score $\in [0, 1]$

Inference latency on a standard laptop CPU is under 100 ms per request. Combined with client-side feature buffering, end-to-end latency remains below 150 ms, enabling potential real-time applications.

6.2 Envisioned Adaptive Interface

While not implemented in this pilot, we envision adaptive interfaces that respond to detected stress by:

- Simplifying visual elements to reduce cognitive load
- Suggesting breaks during sustained high-stress periods
- Adjusting task pacing (e.g., in educational platforms)
- Providing calming feedback (color shifts, reduced notifications)

Validating the effectiveness of such interventions requires controlled user studies, which we leave for future work.

7 Discussion

7.1 Summary of Findings

This pilot study demonstrates that:

1. A Bi-LSTM model trained on keystroke timing features achieves approximately 80% accuracy in distinguishing relaxed vs. stressed typing sessions.
2. Sequential modeling (LSTM) outperforms static classifiers (Random Forest: 76.5%, SVM: 77.2%) on this task, suggesting that temporal patterns in typing rhythm contain discriminative information.
3. Preliminary observations suggest typing under time pressure may exhibit lower variance than relaxed typing, though this requires formal validation.

7.2 Limitations

This work has significant limitations that must be acknowledged:

Sample size and recruitment:

- Small convenience sample ($N = 47$ sessions from ≈ 30 participants) limits statistical power and generalizability.
- No demographic data was collected, we cannot assess how results vary across age, gender, typing experience, or other factors.
- Voluntary participation in “Stressed” condition led to class imbalance (32 relaxed vs. 15 stressed sessions).

Experimental design:

- **No stress validation:** We did not collect self-reported stress measures (e.g., NASA-TLX) or physiological data (e.g., heart rate) to confirm that the “Stressed” condition actually induced stress.
- **Confounded conditions:** Relaxed and Stressed conditions differed in both time pressure AND text content (calming vs. technical). We cannot isolate which factor affects typing patterns.
- **Uncontrolled environment:** Participants used their own devices (desktop and mobile) in uncontrolled settings, introducing noise.

Evaluation methodology:

- **Random split:** Our train/test split was random at the window level, not subject-wise. Windows from the same participant may appear in both sets, potentially inflating accuracy.
- **No cross-validation:** We report single train/test split results rather than k-fold cross-validation, which would provide more robust estimates.
- **Limited metrics:** We did not compute confidence intervals or perform significance testing on model comparisons.

Generalizability:

- Results from college students typing English on QWERTY keyboards may not generalize to other populations, languages, or input methods.
- Controlled paragraph transcription differs from naturalistic typing (emails, creative writing, coding).

7.3 Ethical Considerations

Even in privacy-preserving designs, typing rhythms can serve as biometric identifiers [12]. Any deployment should:

- Obtain informed consent explaining data collection
- Minimize data retention (discard features after inference)
- Avoid coercive deployment (e.g., mandatory workplace monitoring)

8 Future Work

Our long-term vision is to develop **human-responsive computing systems** that automatically adapt to user cognitive and emotional states. This pilot study represents a first step toward that goal. Key directions include:

Immediate improvements:

- Larger, controlled data collection with demographic tracking and validated stress measures (e.g., NASA-TLX, physiological sensors)
- Subject-wise cross-validation to accurately assess generalization
- Controlled experiments isolating time pressure from text complexity

Toward adaptive interfaces:

- Integrate real-time stress detection into web applications, text editors, and educational platforms
- Design and evaluate interventions that reduce cognitive load (simplified UI, break suggestions, pacing adjustments)
- Measure intervention effectiveness through user studies with stress outcomes

Extended applications:

- Multimodal sensing combining keystroke, mouse, and gaze patterns [10]
- Personalized models that adapt to individual typing baselines
- Clinical applications for cognitive fatigue or impairment monitoring [14]

9 Conclusion

This paper presents TypeState, a pilot study exploring whether cognitive load can be detected from keystroke timing patterns. Using a web-based data collector, we gathered 47 typing sessions from college students under relaxed and time-pressured conditions. A Bi-LSTM model trained on flight time and variance features achieved approximately 80% accuracy, outperforming Random Forest (76.5%) and SVM (77.2%) baselines.

While these results are preliminary and limited by small sample size, lack of validated stress measures, and confounded experimental conditions, they suggest that keystroke dynamics may contain useful signals for cognitive state inference. We provide all code, data, and a proof-of-concept inference server to facilitate replication and extension.

Our ultimate goal is human-responsive computing: systems that sense user stress and adapt interfaces in real-time to reduce cognitive burden. This pilot establishes feasibility; rigorous validation remains for future work.

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